

THE USAGE OF ENGLISH BORROWING WORDS IN UZBEK LANGUAGE

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Annotation: This article shows that the usage of English borrowed words in Uzbek language. It includes features and aspects of English words in Uzbek language with some examples.

Annotatsiya: Mazkur maqolada Ingliz tilidan O'zbek tiliga o'zlashgan so'zlar ifodalangan. Maqola ichiga Ingliz tilidagi so'zlarning O'zbek tilida ifodalanish xususiyatlari misollar yordamida yoritilgan.

АННОТАЦИЯ: Эта статья посвящена использованию английских заимствованных слов в узбекском языке. Он включает в себя особенности и аспекты английских слов в узбекском языке с некоторыми примерами.

Key words: borrowings, morphological borrowings, lexical units, linguistics, spelling.

Introduction The Uzbek language developed under the influence of Persian, Arabic and later Russian languages. By studying the loan element in English, as a rule, the emphasis is on the Middle English period, and in Uzbek - on Middle The Turkish language. When we talk about the role of native and borrowed words in language, we must not take into consideration only their number, but their semantic, stylistic character, ability to form words, frequency value, collocability (valence) and productivity of their word formation models.

If we approach the study of the role of native and borrowed words from this point of view, we see, although the native Words are not many, they play an important role in the English and Uzbek languages. They have value, excellent word formation power, broad unity, high frequency, multiple meanings and they are stylistically neutral. Almost all words of indigenous origin belong to very important semantic groups. The number and character of borrowings tell us the relationships between them the peoples, the level of their culture, etc. For this reason, links have often been referred to as historical milestones.

Several Uzbek linguists expressed their ideas on the question of borrowings in the different layers of the language Uzbek language in their works. One of their most important works is "Lexical Layers of Modern Uzbek Literature language" by E. Begmatov. Also, most of our scholars have studied the lexicon of the

modern Uzbek language learned some ideas about borrowing in the language. In particular, in scientific publications such as “Lexicology of the Uzbek language” (1981), published under the edition of A.Khojiev and A.Akhmedov, “Modern Uzbek Literary Language” by H.Jamalkhanov (2005), “Modern Literary Uzbek Language” by Sh.Rakhmatullayev (2006) and “Lexicon of the Old Turks Literary Language” (2015) by B. Abdushukurov, some scientific observations were made on this topic. In addition, most of the dissertations defended in the field of lexicon in recent years have drawn conclusions to some extent and generalizations about borrowed units to some extent. However, in most of the above studies, loans are examined lexically, mainly lexical borrowings are discussed.

Every language, a means of human communication, develops from two different materials. This they are internal sources and external sources. If we look at the development of a particular language, it mostly happens through own internal resources - lexical wealth and grammatical resources. In addition to internal sources, external sources also play an important role in enriching and improving the vocabulary of the Uzbek language. Reference is usually made to external sources enriching vocabulary by borrowing words from other languages. Due to the connection of Uzbek Language with other unrelated languages, a number of words have been borrowed from other languages in Uzbek.

Most linguists began studying the reason for foreign borrowing in the early 20th century. They believe that the main reason for borrowing is to name things and concepts. They also highlighted our main reasons for the occurrence of lexical borrowings in world languages. They are related to: borrowing new things or concepts and duplicating pre-existing words in the language in which they are used. MA Breiter notes that about 15% of last words in English are borrowed due to the lack of a corresponding noun in the target language. They include: **“detector” (valyut), top-model, virtual, investor, daydjest, sponsor, sprej.** The history of the penetration of loan English into Uzbek is closely related to the Russian language, which had a great influence on the development of Uzbek vocabulary in the late 19th and 20th centuries. The first English words came to Uzbek through Russian. In modern English and Uzbek languages, there are hundreds of borrowed words closely associated with history, geography, literature, myths and legends, religion and culture. They are very interesting for linguistic-cultural research, as well as for self-study and for broadening one's horizons. Now the borrowing of English can be found everywhere in modern

Uzbek. In particular, official business documents in the Uzbek language contain many loanwords from English, which play an important role in learning foreign languages. Official documents can be a good example of source or language analysis, as they can indicate the exact moment of their penetration, semantic, graphic and grammatical assimilation into the receiving language. In the following, we classify the words of the thematic group in the areas of social policy, economics, cultural education and sport according to internal structures.

Food Name: Steak, Burger, Yogurt, Cake, Ketchup, Jam, etc.

Fabric Names: Belt, Upright, Rips, Nylon, Blanket, etc.

Designation of vehicles: trolleybus, express, tram, pick-up, liner, trailer, tank.

Scientific terminology: - scientific fields, directional designations: logistics, management, etc.

Economic area and trade: rental, export, tickets, brokers, vouchers, traders, discount, import, importer, investor, budget, marketing, manager, businessman, shop and many others.

Surely, while borrowing new words enriches the conceptual view of the language. And we also have loanwords which take a new word from another language while loanword takes a new word with both source language name and meaning. It is clear that this borrowing helps to develop internal lexicons of the language and also properly influences the culture of the nation. Thus, with the advent of new discoveries, advances in cultural, social, political, spiritual and economic life, as well as advances in technology, have led to the borrowing of new words from the English language, such as broker , barter, briefing, business , deficit, investor, grant, marketing, service, online, offline, computer, printer, internet, website, file, college, high school, high school, bachelor, master, test, multimedia and others.

The mixing of languages, the interaction of one with another, is considered one of the most important linguistic processes. It is clear that with the help of the borrowing of new words, the conceptual vision of the language is enriched in the same way. Also, language learning becomes widespread while penetrating a new culture. Many linguists have proposed a method of studying loanwords based on the linguistic and cultural level of language and culture as the basic structural unit. Every nation has its culture, tradition and of course its cultural memes which reflect the parts of the culture in the language of that nation. These culturemes serve to provide original semantic and linguistic-cultural characteristics of the loanwords. Every person is part of the national culture which includes national traditions, language, history and literature. Studies

dedicated to intercultural communication, to the correlation of language with culture and to linguistic personality are important today. Due to the improvement of all relations between countries and nations and is the result of integration processes taking place around the world.

Analyses of official documents showed that, Uzbek language has borrowed many different lexical elements from English during its development, including international words and newly borrowed units: bill, stendstil, demping, tremping, inaguratsiya, spiker, elektorat, xolding, impichment and many others.

To summarize this brief discussion of borrowed words, it should be emphasized that a linguist cannot, when studying borrowed words settle for establishing the source, the date of penetration, the semantic scope to which the word belonged and the conditions of the loan process. These are all very important, but you also have to be concerned about the changes the new linguistic system that the loanword penetrates causes in the word itself and on the other hand seeks the changes caused by the newcomer in the English vocabulary, as he made his way into the new language some of its lexical neighbors aside. In the discussion above, we have attempted to demonstrate the importance of the compliance issue with the typical patterns of the target language and its semantic requirements. However, the second trend in modern Uzbek linguistics, i.e. the transfer of many words from Uzbek (Turkish) to other languages of the world, is proving to be a real linguistic phenomenon. With this in mind, in this small study, as well as examine the linguistic layers in Uzbek.

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